

IRISCC

D6.4

Report on deployed and launched IRISCC interoperability framework with guidance documentation for service developers

Funded by
the European Union

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Abstract

Keywords

Interoperability, VRE, D4Science

This deliverable, D6.4 details the deployment of the IRISCC Interoperability Framework, built on the D4Science Virtual Research Environment (VRE). It provides a unified platform that simplifies access to data, tools, and computational resources while ensuring scalability, security, and reproducibility.

The IRISCC Interoperability framework is accessible via the IRISCC VRE Gateway (<https://iriscc.d4science.org>), which serves as a central hub for researchers and developers. The Gateway offers key functionalities, including a Shared Workspace for collaborative file management, tailored Virtual Labs (VLabs) for IRISCC demonstrators, and advanced tools like JupyterLab, RStudio, ShinyProxy, and the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP) for executing computational methods. These features streamline workflows, secure data management, and scale computational processes.

Supported by a robust Identity and Access Management (IAM) system, the framework ensures secure and federated access using widely adopted and standard protocols. Integration with external services such as EGI Check-in enhances cross-institutional collaboration while maintaining a secure and consistent user experience.

The report also provides guidance for service developers on deploying customised services and containerised applications, enabling service developers to focus on innovation, fostering collaboration and reproducibility while addressing complex climate challenges.

Revision History

Version	Date	Description	Author/Reviewer
0.1	06/12/24	initial Draft, Table of Contents	Massimiliano Assante (CNR-ISTI)
0.2	19/12/24	Added Introduction	All Authors
0.3	07/01/25	Section 2 and 3 contributions	All Authors

0.4	14/01/25	Section 2 and 3 contributions finalised	All Authors
0.5	16/01/25	Proofreading and quality check	All Authors
0.6	20/01/25	Added executive summary and conclusions	Massimiliano Assante (CNR-ISTI)
0.7	28/01/2025	Review of the report	Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS)
0.8	29/01/2025	Review of the report	Ulrich Bundke (IAGOS/FZJ)
0.9	30/01/2025	Addressed review comments	Massimiliano Assante (CNR-ISTI)
1.0	03/02/2025	Submitted version	Massimiliano Assante (CNR-ISTI)

Document Description			
Report on deployed and launched IRISCC interoperability framework with guidance documentation for service developers (CNR)			
Work Package Number 6			
Document Type	Report		
Document Status	Under EC Review	Version	1.0
Dissemination Level	Public		
Copyright Status	<p>This material by Parties of the IRISCC Consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.</p>		
Lead partner	CNR		
Document Link	https://www.iriscc.eu/publication/d6-4-report-on-IRISCC-interoperability-framework		

DOI	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14777921
Author(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Massimiliano Assante (CNR) • Leonardo Candela (CNR) • Andrea Dell’Amico (CNR) • Luca Frosini (CNR) • Francesco Mangiacrapa (CNR) • Elisa Molinaro (CNR) • Alfredo Oliviero (CNR) • Pasquale Pagano (CNR) • Giancarlo Panichi (CNR) • Biagio Peccerillo (CNR) • Tommaso Piccioli (CNR)
Reviewers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS) • Ulrich Bundke (FZJ)
Approved by:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Noora Parre (Luke)
Estimated Delivery date	Month (M10)
Actual Delivery date	03/02/2025 (M11)

Key Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
CCP	The Cloud Computing Platform is a sophisticated system of distributed components encompassing different technological and operational domains.
CD	Continuous Deployment
CI	Continuous Integration
CLI	Command Line Interface
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud: An open science cloud that provides researchers in Europe with access to data, computing resources, and services.
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable: A set of principles for research data management that ensure data is easily discoverable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IAM	Identity and Access Management
JWT	JSON Web Token
OIDC	Open ID Connect
RBAC	Role Based Access Control
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
RIs	European Research Infrastructures: Research infrastructures are facilities that are essential for conducting research.
SSO	Single Sign On
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

Executive summary

This deliverable, “D6.4 – Report on deployed and launched IRISCC interoperability framework with guidance documentation for service developers”, provides a high-level overview of the IRISCC Interoperability Framework, deployed under Work Package 6 (WP6) of the IRISCC project. The interoperability framework is built on the D4Science [R1, R2, R3] Virtual Research Environment (VRE). It supports collaborative research by offering a unified platform for data management, computational tools, and reproducibility.

At its core, the framework is accessible through the IRISCC VRE Gateway, a web portal available at <https://iriscc.d4science.org>. This gateway acts as a centralised access point for all services and resources, providing functionalities such as a Shared Workspace for collaborative file management, tailored Virtual Labs (VLabs) for the integration of research demonstrator tools, and user-friendly tools like Jupyter Notebooks, RStudio, Shiny Apps, and the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP) to facilitate advanced computational workflows.

The framework is supported by a robust Identity and Access Management (IAM) service that ensures secure and federated access through widely adopted protocols. Integration with external systems, such as the EGI Check-in service, enables cross-institutional collaboration, while secure access controls ensure consistency and compliance across all services.

This report also provides guidance for service developers, such as the IRISCC WP4 Demonstrators [R4], on effectively leveraging the framework. Developers can utilise advanced tools to deploy customised services, containerised applications, and automated workflows. By relying on the framework’s infrastructure for critical functions such as authentication, authorisation, resource monitoring, and scalability, developers can focus on innovation and the creation of impactful solutions. Furthermore, the framework simplifies integration with external resources, enhances collaboration, and reduces operational complexity.

Table of Contents

1.	Introduction.....	8
2.	Interoperability Framework Deployment and Launch.....	10
2.1.	IRISCC VRE Gateway.....	10
2.2.	Virtual Labs	12
2.3.	Identity and Access Management.....	14
2.4.	Cloud Computing Platform for Reproducibility and FAIR Principles	16
2.4.1.	Provenance Management.....	17
2.5.	Deployment process and summary of Key Capabilities of the Framework.....	17
3.	Interoperability Framework guidance for service developers	19
3.1.	JupyterHub: Notebook Servers for JupyterLab, RStudio, and Pluto.jl	19
3.2.	ShinyProxy: Interactive Applications for R and Python	21
3.3.	Custom Containerised Services	22
3.3.1.	Building, publishing, and running services over Docker Swarm	24
3.3.2.	Single Sign-On and Industry-Standard Protocols.....	26
3.3.3.	Auditing and Accounting.....	27
3.3.4.	Monitoring and Metrics.....	29
3.4.	Service Developer Support and VRE Activity Tracker	30
3.5.	REST APIs.....	31
	Conclusions	32
	References	33

Table of Figures

Figure 1. The IRISCC VRE Gateway home page.....	10
Figure 2. The IRISCC VRE Gateway dashboard.....	11
Figure 3. The IRISCC-Lab Virtual Lab as fully functional demonstration.....	13
Figure 4. The IRISCC Login flow	15
Figure 5. Cloud Computing Platform method execution.....	16
Figure 6. JupyterLab showing 2 notebook server options available	20
Figure 7. RStudio IDE opened in the VLab Server on the VRE.....	21
Figure 8. Shiny apps example running over ShinyProxy.....	22
Figure 9. Container Images, Registry and Engine functioning scheme.....	23
Figure 10. Container Running Environment scheme	25
Figure 11. Logical view of the login process	27
Figure 12. NGINX-Based Smart Proxy	28
Figure 13. Prometheus aggregated View via Grafana for the auditing cluster	29
Figure 14. Activity Tracker input form for a new request.....	31

1. Introduction

IRISCC is a Horizon Europe project that aims to provide **Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change risks**. Its goal is to foster cutting-edge research and evidence-based policymaking to improve Europe’s resilience to climate change. The project focuses on developing **scientific and knowledge services** that leverage existing research infrastructures and data to address climate-related challenges.

This document, “*D6.4 – Report on deployed and launched IRISCC interoperability framework with guidance documentation for service developers*”, is produced under Work Package 6 (WP6) of the IRISCC project. WP6’s main goal is to harmonise access procedures for research infrastructures and digital services, as well as to establish and maintain an effective interoperability framework that integrates research infrastructures (RIs), computing, and storage services. The interoperability framework will serve as a valuable platform for the Demonstrators that will be developed with IRISCC WP4, facilitating research integration, collaboration, and open science practices.

Within WP6, Task 6.3 specifically addresses the formulation and deployment of a technical interoperability and FAIRness framework, leveraging the D4Science [R1, R2] Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and other relevant e-infrastructure resources. The aim is to ensure that IRISCC services can be efficiently developed, integrated, and operated to meet FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), and to facilitate cross-RI service provision for climate change risk analysis.

The D4Science VRE is designed to facilitate collaborative scientific research. It provides a centralised platform where researchers from various fields can exchange data, resources, and computational tools. By employing cutting-edge technologies, D4Science enables the integration and interoperability of diverse data sources, paving the way for novel insights and discoveries.

The central D4Science platform is operated by the Institute of Information Science and Technologies (ISTI) of the Italian National Research Council (CNR). CNR-ISTI is a leading research institute in Italy, specialising in information technology and telecommunications. They have been instrumental in developing and maintaining the D4Science VRE as a valuable resource for scientific collaboration.

The D4Science VRE is distinguished by its broad data management capabilities, which form the cornerstone of its support for the entire research lifecycle. Researchers and practitioners can securely upload, store, and manage their datasets, benefitting from high availability and access controls. The platform integrates advanced tools for data analysis, modelling, and visualisation, enabling scientists to extract meaningful insights through customisable workflows. Furthermore, D4Science simplifies data sharing and collaboration, facilitating real-time co-development of projects and efficient knowledge exchange.

In addition, VRE D4Science provides a comprehensive suite of computational resources, including Cloud Computing cluster of servers, specialised software, and support for the on-demand creation and management of Virtual Laboratories. Through these resources, researchers can run complex simulations, analyse large datasets, and create pioneering scientific models. The platform's integration with external services, such as commercial cloud computing providers (i.e., Google Cloud Platform) and various scientific databases, further expands its capabilities and reach.

This report documents:

- The deployment and launch of the IRISCC interoperability framework, accessible via the IRISCC VRE Gateway at <https://iriscc.d4science.org>, that supports integrated services and allows users to exploit them in a coherent and centralised manner.
- The guidance documentation produced for IRISCC service developers, such as the teams developing the WP4 Demonstrators, showcasing how to use the VRE effectively for technical integration and collaboration. By relying on the framework's infrastructure for critical functions developers can focus on innovation and the creation of impactful solutions.

2. Interoperability Framework Deployment and Launch

The deployment and launch of the Interoperability Framework marks a significant milestone in achieving seamless integration across Research Infrastructures (RIs) for climate change risk analysis. Built upon the robust capabilities of the D4Science VRE, the framework ensures compliance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) while promoting harmonised access to scientific resources and services.

Figure 1. The IRISCC VRE Gateway home page

2.1. IRISCC VRE Gateway

All functionalities of the IRISCC Interoperability Framework deployed are accessible through the IRISCC VRE Gateway, a user-friendly web portal available at <https://iriscc.d4science.org/>, the IRISCC VRE Gateway public page is depicted in Figure 1. This gateway serves as the central entry point for end-users to access IRISCC services and Virtual Research Environments, streamlining collaboration, data sharing, and resource management.

The gateway offers the following key functionalities:

- Gateway Home: a central hub where users can collaborate with team members by posting messages, commenting posts.
- Shared Workspace: a collaborative area for storing and sharing files, such as project deliverables, presentations, and datasets. The workspace ensures secure storage and accessibility for data-driven collaboration.

- Virtual Labs (VLABs): Web-based, on-demand environment accessible from within the VRE Gateway, providing tailored services and shared tools to support diverse IRISCC demonstrators.
- User Management: authorised users (VLab Managers) can manage VLab membership by approving new users, assigning or withdrawing roles, removing users, and sending communications to members.
- Members Area: A directory that enables VLab members to view and connect with others in the VRE, fostering collaboration.

Figure 2. The IRISCC VRE Gateway dashboard

The VRE Gateway is designed to simplify user interactions with the IRISCC framework, making it a centralised and intuitive access point for services, tools, and resources.

Figure 2 depicts the current VRE Gateway Dashboard page. The VRE gateway is centred around this Dashboard Page, accessible after the login. The Dashboard Page offers users an integrated view of the entire IRISCC VRE ecosystem, enabling efficient navigation and seamless access to tools, services, and resources.

Specifically, the Dashboard Page includes:

- **Access to Demonstrator VLABs:** Provides direct links to Virtual Labs tailored to specific demonstrators, and their descriptions, allowing users to leverage pre-configured tools and services for targeted workflows.
- **Shared Workspace Overview:** A quick view of shared files and folders, enabling users to manage and collaborate on datasets and research outputs efficiently.
- **User Shared Workspace:** A cloud-based file system supporting folder management and sharing of various item types, such as binary files, workflows, and tabular data. Each user can upload files, while project coordinators can organise them in shared folders accessible to all project members. It supports file

management, version control (each item is automatically versioned), collaboration, offering a seamless experience for research workflows. It supports three folder types, allowing users to manage access to their materials:

- Private Folders: Accessible only by the owner;
- Shared Folders: Accessible to selected users;
- VRE Folders: Available to all members of a given VLab.

It is fully integrated with D4Science services, ensuring smooth interaction between data storage, computational tools, and collaborative platforms. In particular, connects with key computational tools such as JupyterLab, RStudio, and the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP) which will be introduced in the following, enabling researchers to seamlessly use their stored data within various analytical applications.

- **Private Messages:** An integrated email-like service that allows users to communicate efficiently. This feature is deeply integrated with the Shared Workspace, enabling users to attach and share large, complex objects directly from the workspace without consuming bandwidth.
- **User Profile and Account:** A customisation area where users can update their personal information, biographical details, and notification preferences to tailor the VRE experience to their needs.
- **Notifications:** Centralised alerts to keep users informed about updates, activities, and relevant tasks within the VRE. These notifications are designed to provide users with timely updates about events that are directly relevant to their work.

2.2. Virtual Labs

Virtual Labs (VLabs), accessible directly from within the IRISCC VRE Gateway, offer web-based, on-demand environments that unify external systems such as data repositories, storage solutions, and cloud-based infrastructures into a cohesive web environment. These VLabs are specifically designed to provide researchers with tailored services and tools to meet the diverse needs of IRISCC demonstrators, facilitating cross-domain collaboration and innovation.

VLabs leverage external systems and expose them as a common unified resource space, providing researchers with:

- **Tailored Services:** VLabs are customised to meet the specific needs of IRISCC demonstrators, enabling workflows that address targeted climate change risk analysis scenarios.

- **Integration of Resources:** external systems, such as data repositories, storage, and computational infrastructures, are seamlessly integrated and made accessible as part of the unified workspace.
- **Collaboration and Sharing:** V Labs act as collaborative environments where users can share tools, datasets, and analysis results, fostering teamwork and accelerating research.

By integrating V Labs into the IRISCC framework and making them accessible via the VRE Gateway, researchers can focus on their scientific workflows without being burdened by the complexities of resource management, ensuring a streamlined and efficient research process.

Figure 3. The IRISCC-Lab Virtual Lab as fully functional demonstration

At the time of writing (M10), one exemplar VLab is available within the IRISCC VRE: the IRISCC-Lab VLab, which Home is depicted in Figure 3. This VLab serves as a **fully functional demonstration of the IRISCC Interoperability Framework’s capabilities**, offering users a unified and collaborative workspace tailored to the needs of research teams.

This VLab Home provides an intuitive and user-friendly interface designed to foster collaboration and enhance productivity. Key features of the IRISCC-Lab VLab include:

- **VRE Shared Folder:** a dedicated shared cloud storage space accessible to all VLab members. This folder allows users to upload, share, and organise files and datasets critical to their collaborative projects. The shared folder streamlines teamwork by ensuring that all project-related resources are easily accessible and centrally managed.

- **Posts Feed:** a dynamic posts feed enabling collaboration and communication among VLab members. Users can post messages, comment on updates, and react to co-workers' contributions.
- **VLab abstract:** a detailed overview of the VLab purpose and functionality is displayed on the home page.
- **Navigation Bar and Tools:** The navigation bar provides easy access to the key tools and features that the IRISCC-Lab VLab makes available to its members. These tools include:
 - JupyterLab: a powerful interactive development environment for running Jupyter Notebooks, enabling advanced data analysis, visualisation, and computation.
 - RStudio: a popular integrated development environment for R, supporting statistical analysis and the creation of reproducible research outputs.
 - Analytics Engine: a tool for executing advanced computational workflows and large-scale data analysis based on the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP) technology, which provides scalable and reproducible execution environments for computational tasks. Details on the CCP and its integration within the Analytics Engine will be discussed in the following sections.
 - Members Directory: A comprehensive list of all VLab members, facilitating collaboration by enabling users to connect and communicate with their peers.
 - How-To Documentation

The plan is to configure and deploy individual VLabs for each WP4 Demonstrator.

2.3. Identity and Access Management

Identity and Access Management (IAM) is at the core of the framework, providing a robust and secure mechanism for user authentication and authorisation. The interoperability framework adopts industry-standard protocols such as **OAuth2** and **OpenID Connect** (OIDC) to enable **Single Sign-On** (SSO) across integrated services.

Figure 4. The IRISCC Login flow

These protocols streamline the user experience by allowing secure and token-based access without requiring users to repeatedly authenticate for each service. The IAM system also supports identity federation, enabling users to log in using their institutional or social credentials (e.g., Google, LinkedIn). Additionally, the IAM integrates with the **EGI Check-in service**, which facilitates access for users from the European research community (e.g. EOSC), streamlining cross-institutional collaboration and interoperability. By centralising identity management and ensuring secure access control, the IAM system fosters a cohesive and user-friendly environment for researchers.

As shown in Figure 4, when users try to log in, they are redirected to a secure login page provided by the system's Identity and Access Management (IAM). If they are not already logged in through another service (Single Sign-On or SSO), they will be asked to enter their username and password. Once they successfully log in, they are taken back to the application they were accessing with their identity recognised.

The deployment process involved a structured approach, starting with the configuration of the D4Science VRE infrastructure and the integration of services using containerisation and orchestration. Tools like JupyterHub and ShinyProxy were deployed to support scalable, containerised applications, while continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) pipelines ensured consistent and efficient service updates. Data management workflows were established to ensure compatibility with FAIR principles, while the IAM system was integrated to enforce secure access policies.

2.4. Cloud Computing Platform for Reproducibility and FAIR Principles

The Cloud Computing Platform (CCP, <https://ccp.cloud.d4science.org/docs/index.html>) is a key enabler for advancing reproducibility and ensuring adherence to FAIR principles within the IRISCC framework. CCP provides a robust infrastructure for executing computational methods and algorithms at scale. By leveraging a microservice-based architecture, CCP fosters flexibility and interoperability, allowing researchers to deploy and manage custom algorithms seamlessly.

Key features of CCP include the **methods importer** tool, which simplifies the integration of computational methods, and the execution lifecycle tracker, which meticulously documents every stage of **method execution** to ensure transparency and traceability. Researchers can monitor processes in real time using the execution monitor, providing live feedback during execution, and leverage the platform’s archiving capabilities to preserve configurations and inputs for future reproducibility. Figure 5 shows the CCP Method Execution front-end.

Figure 5. Cloud Computing Platform method execution

The CCP supports a wide range of execution infrastructures, including High-Performance Computing (HPC) clusters, commercial cloud platforms (e.g., Google Cloud Platform), and local environments. By adopting containerisation technologies like Docker and Kubernetes, CCP ensures portability, scalability, and consistency across various execution contexts. This

flexibility allows researchers to optimise computational workloads, aligning resource use with data locality and computational demand.

2.4.1. Provenance Management

Provenance management records the lineage and processing history of research data, providing essential insights into data generation, transformation, and analysis. The CCP automatically captures and maintains provenance metadata for each method execution, ensuring transparency and reproducibility in data-driven research.

To standardise and structure provenance information, CCP leverages the PROV Ontology (PROV-O, <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>), an OWL2-based formalization of the W3C PROV Data Model. This enables precise representation of entities, activities, and agents involved in computational workflows, ensuring data quality, reliability, and trustworthiness.

Aligned with FAIR principles, the CCP automatically generates and stores PROV-compliant XML files alongside method executions in the User Shared Workspace (cf. sec. 2.1). These records include input/output data, parameters, and metadata, enabling users to seamlessly reproduce and repeat computational tasks. This built-in provenance tracking is fundamental for workflow repeatability within the VRE, ensuring that each analytical process is transparent and verifiable.

Researchers and developers can access provenance records to validate results, review complete execution histories, and assess the impact of parameter configurations and tool choices. These records stored within the User Shared Workspace provide a traceable and verifiable research trail, reinforcing scientific integrity and reproducibility.

2.5. Deployment process and summary of Key Capabilities of the Framework

The deployment process of the IRISCC Interoperability Framework followed a structured approach, starting with the configuration of the D4Science VRE infrastructure and the integration of containerised services. Tools like JupyterHub and ShinyProxy were deployed to enable scalable and efficient execution of computational methods, while CI/CD pipelines ensured consistent updates.

The IAM system reinforced secure and federated access policies, including support for EGI Check-in, while CCP facilitated reproducibility and scalability through advanced computational capabilities.

- **Centralised Access:** the IRISCC VRE Gateway consolidates all tools, services, and collaborative features into a single access point.
- **Integrated Dashboard:** the personalised Dashboard Page streamlines user workflows by providing quick access to key facilities, such as Shared Workspace, Demonstrator VLabs, and Private Messages.
- **Virtual Labs (VLabs):** tailored environments for demonstrators that integrate external resources and services into unified workspaces.
- **Shared Workspace:** Cloud-based file management supporting collaborative sharing of datasets, workflows, and other objects.
- **Secure Access Management:** IAM utilises protocols like OAuth2 and OIDC and integrates with EGI Check-in for federated and secure access.
- **Advanced Cloud Computing Platform:** CCP supports efficient execution of methods, ensuring reproducibility and FAIR compliance.

By combining these elements, the IRISCC Interoperability Framework fosters collaboration, innovation, and reproducibility, empowering researchers to address climate challenges effectively.

3. Interoperability Framework guidance for service developers

The IRISCC Interoperability Framework, built on the robust D4Science platform, is designed to provide seamless integration and interoperability for service developers. This approach not only enhances the user experience but also ensures high standards of scalability, security, and reliability, creating a stable foundation for innovation.

Service developers, such as the IRISCC WP4 Demonstrator developers, have access to a range of options for customising VRE services, grouped into three main categories:

- **JupyterHub:** the JupyterHub (<https://jupyter.org/hub>) service enables the deployment of dedicated and customised notebook servers for various environments, including JupyterLab, RStudio Server, and Pluto.jl (<https://plutojl.org>). This flexibility supports diverse workflows and programming languages.
- **ShinyProxy:** the ShinyProxy (<https://www.shinyproxy.io>) service facilitates the execution of interactive applications, such as Shiny apps (developed in R or Python) and Dash apps (<https://dash.plotly.com>, primarily developed in Python using Plotly).
- **Custom Containerised Services:** beyond JupyterHub and ShinyProxy, developers can deploy fully customised services using containerisation. By building and configuring containers tailored to specific requirements, services can be integrated into the VRE and orchestrated efficiently using Docker Swarm. Docker Swarm was chosen primarily due to its simplicity, ease of setup, and lower operational overhead, making it more convenient for service developers. Docker Swarm offers a more lightweight and straightforward approach to container orchestration, which is particularly beneficial for teams that do not require the full complexity of Kubernetes. It provides seamless service scaling, built-in load balancing, and native Docker CLI integration, making it faster to deploy and manage within our infrastructure.

Additionally, the D4Science VRE leverages containerisation, container orchestration, standardised Identity and Access Management (IAM), and continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) pipelines. These technologies streamline the development and deployment process, significantly reducing operational overhead. As a result, developers can focus on building innovative solutions that advance scientific research within a collaborative and efficient environment.

3.1. JupyterHub: Notebook Servers for JupyterLab, RStudio, and Pluto.jl

JupyterHub in the VRE provides an adaptable framework for hosting interactive computational environments tailored to the needs of researchers and developers. It is not

limited to JupyterLab but also supports customisations for other popular environments such as RStudio Server and Pluto.jl, making it a versatile choice for various scientific and data-intensive workflows.

Figure 6. JupyterLab showing 2 notebook server options available

Key Features and Capabilities:

- **Customised Notebook Servers:** Each user can access a dedicated notebook server configured with the specific libraries, tools, and programming languages required for their tasks. This eliminates conflicts and ensures a consistent working environment. An example is given in Figure 6.
- **JupyterLab Support:** Users can leverage JupyterLab (<https://jupyter.org>) for multi-language notebook development, real-time collaboration, and interactive data visualisation. This is ideal for Python-based workflows and exploratory data analysis.
- **RStudio Server Integration:** For R users, JupyterHub supports customised RStudio Server environments. These servers are preloaded with the necessary R packages and can be tailored to handle statistical analysis, data visualisation, and advanced modelling tasks. An example is given in Figure 7.
- **Pluto.jl Support:** Developers working with Julia can use Pluto.jl, an interactive notebook environment for scientific computing. Pluto.jl notebooks are reactive, ensuring that changes in one part of the code update outputs in real-time, making it particularly effective for teaching and exploratory work.

Figure 7. RStudio IDE opened in the VLab Server on the VRE

3.2. ShinyProxy: Interactive Applications for R and Python

ShinyProxy in the VRE enables the deployment of interactive web applications that provide dynamic data exploration and visualisation capabilities. This service supports both Shiny apps developed in R or Python and Dash apps created with Plotly in Python, offering a versatile environment for developing user-friendly tools tailored to scientific research and decision-making needs.

While Shiny Apps provide interactive dashboards for statistical analysis, real-time monitoring, and visualising trends in environmental or climate data, Dash Apps provide advanced Python-based applications for creating highly interactive and customised visualisation tools, such as simulation platforms or decision-support systems for climate research.

Advantages of ShinyProxy in the VRE

Because the VRE takes care of these foundational services, service developers using ShinyProxy do not need to implement or maintain custom solutions for user authentication, authorisation, access control, or monitoring. This delegation significantly reduces overhead, enabling developers to focus entirely on designing and enhancing their applications. The result is a streamlined development and deployment process that adheres to high standards of security, scalability, and FAIR principles.

Figure 8. Shiny apps example running over ShinyProxy

ShinyProxy, as illustrated in Figure 8 demonstrates the deployment of Shiny apps for interactive data exploration and visualisation. These applications, combined with the robust infrastructure of the VRE, provide researchers with powerful tools for engaging with complex datasets and advancing collaborative research.

Key Features and Capabilities:

- **Support for Multiple Frameworks:** ShinyProxy is compatible with Shiny apps (R) and Dash apps (Python), offering flexibility for developers to use their preferred programming language and framework.
- **Customisation:** Developers can create highly tailored applications by preloading containers with specific dependencies, datasets, and configurations.
- **Secure Deployment:** Applications run within containerised environments, ensuring isolation and security. The VRE integrates ShinyProxy with its Identity and Access Management (IAM) system, enabling secure access control for deployed apps.
- **Scalability:** ShinyProxy dynamically scales the number of running instances based on user demand. This ensures that applications remain responsive, even during peak usage.

3.3. Custom Containerised Services

The VRE allows developers to deploy fully customised containerised services, providing the ultimate flexibility for integrating specialised tools and applications. By leveraging containerisation, developers can package applications with all their dependencies and configurations, ensuring consistent performance across environments.

This section provides an overview of the processes and technologies involved in integrating custom applications and services into the VRE. Containerization is the core method of integrating custom applications. By packaging an application and its dependencies into self-contained containers, developers can guarantee consistent behaviour across various

deployment environments—an essential requirement in research computing where the software stack can be extremely diverse.

The integration of containerised applications relies on three primary components: **container images**, **container engines**, and **container registries**.

As shown in Figure 9, **Container images** encapsulate all necessary binaries, libraries, and configuration files to ensure applications run consistently across diverse environments, enhancing reproducibility and avoiding version conflicts. These images are managed using **Docker**, the primary **container engine** employed by D4Science, which offers mature tooling and integration with both CLI and API workflows, supporting automated pipelines and local testing with tools like **Docker Compose**.

To store and manage these images, D4Science utilises both public **container registries**, such as Docker Hub, and a dedicated Harbor-based registry at <https://harbor.d4science.org/>. Harbor enhances security with image vulnerability scanning, version tagging, and role-based access control (RBAC), enabling service developers to maintain secure and centrally stored images while also allowing for private repositories to safeguard proprietary applications. Together, these components form the foundation of a scalable, secure, and efficient containerisation framework.

Figure 9. Container Images, Registry and Engine functioning scheme

Container Orchestration

To manage containerised applications at scale, D4Science relies on container orchestration tools, including Kubernetes and Docker Swarm. These tools automate tasks such as deployment, scaling, and resource allocation, ensuring efficient operation within the VRE.

The following section specifically refers to the use of Docker Swarm for orchestrating containerised services as available to service developers.

3.3.1. Building, publishing, and running services over Docker Swarm

Running services within the Docker Swarm cluster follows a structured and well-defined process, designed to ensure both reliability and scalability. This approach guarantees consistent service deployment, efficient scaling, and smooth maintenance with minimal downtime, enabling seamless integration and high availability throughout the VRE.

When creating container images, following best practices is essential to enhance security and efficiency. **Security vulnerabilities** can be mitigated by avoiding unnecessary privileges in the image, using trusted base images, and excluding sensitive information, such as API keys or passwords. Additionally, **minimising image size** not only improves build times but also reduces the time taken to push images to the registry and pull them into the Docker node.

Consolidating instructions in the Dockerfile to **reduce the number of layers** further contributes to this efficiency. It is also advisable to **scan images for vulnerabilities** using tools like Docker Scan or Clair and include health checks in the image to ensure services run smoothly.

Publishing and Storing Container Images

Once built, container images need to be published to a registry. The VRE supports both public and private registries for this purpose.

Public registries, such as Docker Hub, are ideal for open-source applications. As explained in the previous section the VRE provides a dedicated Harbor-based registry for secure and controlled storage of private images, available at <https://harbor.d4science.org/>, which is recommended.

This registry enhances security by performing automated vulnerability scans and offers role-based access control to manage team permissions effectively. Version tagging allows developers to maintain a clear history of image updates and releases, streamlining the management of application versions. For each Demonstrator, a dedicated project could be created on the container registry.

Container Running Environment in the VRE

The container running environment in the VRE is structured to ensure secure, scalable, and efficient service operations. The interaction between clients, load balancers, containers, and external resources is tightly orchestrated to maintain high performance and security standards.

Figure 10. Container Running Environment scheme

As depicted in Figure 10, clients send requests to the external load balancers.

- The external load balancers forward traffic to the Docker HAProxy instances inside the Docker Swarm cluster.
- HAProxy terminates HTTPS and directs requests to the appropriate containers based on the service configuration.
- Containers interact internally using a dedicated network, while external storage volumes connect directly to containers requiring persistent data.

External Client Interaction

Clients communicate with services hosted in the VRE through an **external Layer 4 load balancer**, which proxies all requests to the Docker HAProxy load balancers within the Docker Swarm cluster. These HAProxy load balancers terminate HTTPS connections, ensuring that all traffic between the client and the services runs securely over HTTPS.

Internal Communication Between Containers

Containers within a service communicate using a dedicated internal-only network. This internal network isolates service components, providing a secure communication channel that is inaccessible from outside the cluster. Containers exposing public endpoints must be explicitly connected to the HAProxy load balancer network to ensure external accessibility.

Integration with External Storage

For persistent data storage, containers are connected to external storage volumes. This setup decouples the application data from the container image, ensuring that data remains intact even if containers are recreated or updated. In the example diagram, the app-container-backend is connected to an external storage volume (/backend-volume), which allows seamless integration of persistent data storage into the containerized service architecture.

3.3.2. Single Sign-On and Industry-Standard Protocols

The IRISCC VRE employs a robust Identity and Access Management (IAM) layer featuring:

- **OpenID Connect, OAuth 2.0, and SAML:** Enabling seamless authentication and authorization flows.
- **Identity Brokering:** Users can log in through federated or social identity providers, simplifying credential management, including the **EGI Check-in service**

For service developers, adhering to these protocols means ensuring that your application can parse JSON Web Tokens (JWT) or security assertions as part of the request flow. Token management libraries (e.g., node-openid-client for Node.js, Spring Security OAuth2 for Java) streamline integration.

The Keycloak (<https://www.keycloak.org>) open-source technology has been chosen as the implementation of the **Identity and Authorization Manager (IAM)**, the main service for the Authorization and Authentication parts of the Security System. Keycloak is an industry ready, widely adopted open-source implementation providing most of the models and workflows underpinning modern authentication and authorization management.

Figure 11 shows an abstract representation of the way the IRISCC VRE authenticates a User who is accessing the platform.

Figure 11. Logical view of the login process

Users access the IRISCC VRE Gateway through front-facing applications known as Gateways. Authentication is handled via the authorization code grant flow defined by OAuth2, ensuring that neither user credentials nor those of the gateway service are shared with software outside the Identity and Access Management (IAM) system.

User agents (browsers) are redirected to login forms provided by the IAM. If users are not already signed in through other gateways (SSO), they are prompted to enter their credentials (Cred), typically a username and password. At the conclusion of the workflow, users are redirected back to the Gateway, where their credentials are exchanged for a JWT Access Token (AT). This token conveys the user’s identity and roles to the Gateway and enables authorised calls to backend services without requiring additional user credentials. To exploit this functionality service developers need an OpenID-configuration Well-known URI (<https://accounts.d4science.org/auth/realms/d4science/.well-known/openid-configuration>) and must be authorised by the IRISCC VRE Administrators. Service developers can issue a request through the Activity Tracker (cf. sec. 3.4)

3.3.3. Auditing and Accounting

Auditing and accounting are critical components of the D4Science VRE, enabling transparency, compliance, and responsible resource usage. By collecting and analysing anonymised detailed records of user actions, requests, and resource consumption, platform both administrators and service developers gain insights into how the VRE is being utilised.

Several technologies can facilitate auditing and accounting within a containerized environment. NGINX-based Smart Proxy is one such approach, but others (e.g., HAProxy, Traefik, Envoy) can also be considered. The key is to intercept and log requests passing through the VRE.

Figure 12. NGINX-Based Smart Proxy

NGINX-Based Smart Proxy is strategically placed at the edge of the service to intercept incoming requests. When traffic is intercepted, the proxy captures user session data (e.g., user ID, token information) and request metadata (e.g., request path, timestamp, payload size). These requests are then forwarded to an auditing service or database for logging and compliance purposes.

By consolidating authentication checks at the proxy layer (in conjunction with IAM tokens), as shown in Figure 12, the system enforces consistent security policies across multiple containerised services. This centralised approach not only ensures robust security but also reduces the complexity for individual services.

A **significant advantage** of the Smart Proxy is that a **custom service** deployed in the IRISCC VRE **does not need to manage its own authentication and authorisation mechanisms**. These tasks are absorbed by the Smart Proxy, which verifies user credentials and session tokens before forwarding requests to the service. This enables service developers to focus on the core functionality of their applications without having to implement and maintain custom access control logic, thereby simplifying development and enhancing overall security.

The Smart Proxy thus serves as a powerful intermediary, streamlining both security and operational workflows while ensuring that all services within the VRE adhere to consistent, high standards of compliance and usability.

3.3.4. Monitoring and Metrics

Prometheus (<https://prometheus.io/>) is the foundation of monitoring and alerting within the VRE, providing a powerful and flexible system for observing and managing service performance. Its multi-dimensional metrics capability allows developers to define custom metrics, such as the number of processed requests or the size of datasets, enabling precise measurement of application behaviour. These metrics are queried and analysed using PromQL, a robust query language that supports the aggregation, filtering, and correlation of data to uncover meaningful insights. Additionally, Prometheus integrates seamlessly with Alert manager, a tool that generates notifications—via email, Slack, or other channels—whenever predefined thresholds, such as high CPU usage, are exceeded. This ensures timely alerts and rapid response to potential issues.

Figure 13. Prometheus aggregated View via Grafana for the auditing cluster

Complementing Prometheus, **Grafana** (<https://grafana.com/>) provides an intuitive interface for visualising the collected data through dashboards, an example is given in Figure 13. These dashboards transform time-series metrics into interactive charts and graphs, offering real-time insights into system performance.

Grafana supports shared dashboards, allowing teams to collaboratively troubleshoot and optimize services by analysing the same datasets. To ensure security and relevance, Grafana also includes role-based access control, enabling specific dashboards to be

restricted to administrators or tailored to the needs of individual project teams. Together, Prometheus and Grafana deliver a comprehensive and user-friendly monitoring solution that empowers developers and operators to maintain high-performing, reliable services within the VRE.

3.4. Service Developer Support and VRE Activity Tracker

The VRE Activity Tracker is a part of the IRISCC Interoperability Framework, service developers may encounter challenges, require new resources, or wish to report incidents. To facilitate these needs, the IRISCC framework provides a dedicated support platform: the VRE Activity Tracker, accessible at <https://support.d4science.org/projects/iriscc-support>.

Figure 14 shows a page of the Activity Tracker, which is based on the Redmine technology (<https://www.redmine.org>), a well-tested platform with tools for detailed tracking, role management, and community interaction, and centralises all communication and support tickets related to IRISCC development activities.

The Activity Tracker ties seamlessly into the IAM, ensuring that each request is associated with a valid user identity, and it is based on tickets. Tickets ensure systematic handling of issues and requests by using this platform, developers can ensure a timely response from VRE experts, maintain a clear audit trail of requests and resolutions, and foster efficient collaboration across teams.

Ticket Request Types

When creating a request, service developers are prompted to select from one of the four main categories:

1. **Incident:** typically refers to unexpected service downtime, software malfunctions, or infrastructure-related errors that impede normal operations.
2. **Support:** for general queries, troubleshooting steps, or requests for guidance that do not qualify as active system failures.
3. **Docker Image:** for deployment and updating of Docker images for IRISCC services.
4. **Database:** when developers need to request database storage for their services.

Figure 14. Activity Tracker input form for a new request

Ticket Priority and Status

The service developers can set the priority (e.g., Low, Normal, High, Urgent) to indicate how urgent the request is, while the support team can then track the ticket status (e.g., New, In Progress, Feedback, Resolved, Closed).

3.5. REST APIs

D4Science provides a suite of REST APIs, available at <https://dev.d4science.org>, designed to facilitate seamless integration, interoperability, and the efficient development of services within its VRE. These APIs empower developers by simplifying interactions with key infrastructure components, enabling them to focus on creating robust and impactful solutions.

The REST APIs simplify the integration of external applications and services with the VRE. They offer developers powerful tools to build applications that interact with critical resources such as user workspaces, metadata catalogues, and geospatial datasets.

Conclusions

The deployment and launch of the IRISCC Interoperability Framework represent a significant achievement in advancing the integration and harmonisation of Research Infrastructures (RIs) for climate change risk analysis. Built on the D4Science Virtual Research Environment (VRE), this framework establishes a unified, secure, and scalable ecosystem for researchers, enabling seamless collaboration, reproducibility, and compliance with FAIR principles.

The IRISCC VRE Gateway serves as the centralised access point for all framework functionalities, offering a user-friendly and intuitive platform. Through features such as the Shared Workspace, Virtual Labs (VLabs), researchers can efficiently manage data, collaborate with peers, and leverage tailored services for their specific needs. The integration of tools like JupyterHub, ShinyProxy, and the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP) highlights the framework's emphasis on flexibility and innovation, supporting diverse computational workflows and enabling reproducible research at scale.

A key strength of the IRISCC framework is its Identity and Access Management (IAM) system, which ensures secure and federated access using industry-standard protocols like OAuth2 and OpenID Connect. By integrating with external services such as the EGI Check-in, the IAM system facilitates cross-institutional collaboration, making the VRE accessible to a broad range of users while maintaining stringent security measures. Additionally, features such as auditing and accounting, delegated to the Smart Proxy, further enhance security and usability by alleviating the burden on individual services.

The adoption of containerisation and orchestration technologies, particularly Docker Swarm and Kubernetes, ensures consistent deployment, efficient scaling, and high availability of services within the VRE. Complemented by monitoring and metrics tools like Prometheus and Grafana, the framework enables real-time performance tracking and proactive issue resolution, ensuring reliable and high-performing services for all users.

Moving forward, the IRISCC VRE will continue to evolve, offering enhanced capabilities and supporting the broader research community in achieving impactful and reproducible outcomes.

References	
No	Description/Link
R1	Assante M., Candela L., D. Castelli D., R. Cirillo R., G. Coro G., L. Frosini L., L. Lelii L., F. Mangiacrapa F., Pagano P., Panichi G., Sinibaldi F. (2019) Enacting open science by D4Science . Future Gener. Comput. Syst. 101: 555–563 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.05.063
R2	M. Assante et al. (2023) Virtual research environments co-creation: The D4Science experience. Concurrency Computat Pract Exper. 2023; 35(18): e6925. https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.6925
R3	Bundke, U., Schaap, D., & Krijger, T. (2024). Analysis report of D4Science VRE fitness for purpose and adaptations required (v1.0 Public Under EC Review). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13866276
R4	Kivekäs, N., Schaap, D., Pagé, C., Verlaan, M., Vermeulen, R., Vereecken, H., Poppe Terán, C., Serret Ituarte, P., Klem, K., & Mona, L. (2024). Report on the full Demonstrator design (v1.0 Public Under EC Review). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880714